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Predictions of macro-scale fracture geometries from acoustic emission point cloud data in a hydraulic fracturing experiment

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4 **Abstract** Observations of laboratory fracture testing by means of acoustic emission (AE) can
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6 provide a wealth of information regarding the fracturing process and the subsequent damage of the
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8 material or structure under load. A method for determining the structure of macro-scale fractures
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10 from a point cloud of AE events was developed and tested at the laboratory scale. An unconfined
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12 hydraulic fracturing experiment was performed on granite while monitoring acoustic emissions
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14 from six piezoelectric transducers on the surfaces of the specimen. The granite specimen
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16 dimensions were 30x30x25 cm³. The motivation of the AE analysis was to provide location
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18 information for a secondary wellbore placement which intersects the hydraulic fracture to
19
20 complete a hydraulically connected binary well-hydraulic fracture system. Information gained
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22 from the 3D event source locations was used to optimize the location and orientation of secondary
23
24 production well placement to intersect the induced hydraulic fracture. A direct method was
25
26 developed to predict the location, orientation and shape of the hydraulic fracture from a dense
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28 cloud of AE events. The predicted fracture plane, which was assumed to be planar, was rotated in
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30 both the pitch and roll directions, while an average error of AE event distance between the assumed
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32 plane and the individual event locations was determined for each rotation iteration, resulting with
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34 a predicted fracture plane in the minimum error orientation. Post-test fracture observations were
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36 made and digitized in 3D space from coring and slabbing the granite specimen. The actual fracture
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38 observations were compared with the predicted fracture structure from AE and showed marked
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40 correlation. The simple method of determining macro-scale fracture location, orientation, and
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42 extents provided a useful tool for materials that exhibit large and disperse clouds of AE activity
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44 where coalesced fracture structure is not apparent.
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55 **Keywords** acoustic emission, hydraulic fracturing, microseismic, fracture geometry, scale-model
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57 experiments
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INTRODUCTION

Hydraulic fracturing is a standard practice in oil-, gas-, and geothermal heat bearing formations to increase reservoir permeability due to the commonality of micro and nanodarcy permeability in many of these reservoirs. Introducing hydraulic fractures in oftentimes complex environments of stress and rock structure makes predictions of hydraulically connected and accessed fractures difficult. Predictions of induced and activated natural fracture geometries are important for determining stimulation effectiveness, geometry of the connected reservoir structure, drainage predictions, and provide a useful metric for stimulation procedure alteration for future treatments in similar formations or fields. Several methods exist for monitoring hydraulic fracturing treatments and obtaining information regarding the geometry of the induced subsurface changes including microseismic, microdeformation, fiber optic distributed acoustic sensing, and others. Microseismic observations provide source locations of individual fractures occurring within an observable frequency bandwidth (Shapiro et al, 2006; SanLinn et al., 2017; Eisner et al., 2013; Warpinski, 2009; Maxwell et al. 2002; Meyehofer et al., 2010; Ishida et al., 2012; Ma et al., 2017). Although these observations can sometimes provide a substantial amount of fracture data, they are limited in observation to energy released in a specified wave frequency. It is estimated that much of the fracture deformation and energy release throughout a hydraulic fracturing treatment is aseismic (Maxwell et al., 2009; Warpinski et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2018). Though microseismic observations do not provide the entire story behind a hydraulic fracturing treatment, they often provide significant numbers of located fracture events in which further analysis can be performed.

Several methodologies exist for extracting induced fracture network location information from a cloud of microseismic events, including stimulated reservoir volume (SRV) estimation,

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4 clustering geometries, discrete fracture network (DFN) estimation, collapsing, and others
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6 (Zimmer, 2011; Maxwell, 2011; Jones and Stewart, 1997; Microseismic Inc., 2011; Tsangouri et
7
8 al., 2015). SRV estimation is typically performed through binning and shrink-wrapping methods,
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10 where hydraulic connection is either assumed between the wellbore and a microseismic event if
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12 enough events occupy the space between them, or assuming a hydraulic connection within a whole
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14 cloud of events based on proximity relationships, respectively. These cloud-based techniques are
15
16 valuable for qualitative analyses of stimulation effectiveness and reservoir drainage estimations,
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18 but lack in actual fracture geometry predictions. In the literature (Microseismic Inc., 2011) DFN
19
20 predictions have been made from individual microseismic event moment tensor solutions and
21
22 determined fault plane predictions. The fault planes for individual events are plotted as their own
23
24 discrete fracture planes and the cloud of microseismic events becomes a cloud of individual fault
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26 plane solutions. These fault planes are then often assumed to be a complex group of separate but
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28 interacting fractures. Though obtaining fault plane solutions for individual events is valuable,
29
30 assuming each event is part of a separate and competing macro-scale fracture is an
31
32 oversimplification. Individual microseismic event observations can be attributed to the main
33
34 hydraulic fracture growth, but also can be stress- or leakoff-induced natural fracture activation,
35
36 secondary fracturing occurring non-planar to the main hydraulic fracture, among others. The
37
38 inability to distinguish which type of fracture is observed from microseismic observations makes
39
40 macro-scale DFN estimation from single fault plane solutions difficult. It is also often assumed
41
42 that the microseismic events also stem not from the main hydraulic fracture growth, which in many
43
44 cases is a slow aseismic tensile opening, but rather from, the induced fractures surrounding the tip
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46 of the progressing fracture in the shear stress dominated zone along with slip at pre-existing
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48 surfaces or sliding on the newly induced hydraulic fracture behind the fracture tip. This would
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4 mean that fracture plane predictions from individual microseismic event fault plane solutions
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6 would be oriented at a wide array of angles from the progressing hydraulic fracture. Though DFNs
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8 created from single events can be difficult to interpret, macro-scale fracture estimation from
9
10 groupings of individual microseismic events can provide reasonable estimations of actual fracture
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12 geometries, especially in terms of having possible identifications of the slow tensile opening main
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14 fractures that oftentimes reside within a large cloud of located events.
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19 In this work, predictions of coalesced fractures were determined by fitting a plane to a
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21 cloud of acoustic emission data from a laboratory hydraulic fracture test. AE refers to the
22
23 generation of transient elastic waves in a material caused by the sudden occurrence of fractures or
24
25 frictional sliding along discontinuous surfaces (Mogi, 2007), and is a higher frequency analog to
26
27 microseismic monitoring. AE testing illuminates microcracking and relatively small failures in a
28
29 material under loading in real-time. Although the AE method for determining the initiation and/or
30
31 propagation of flaws or friction processes is informative, a disadvantage of the AE method is that
32
33 a particular test or microcrack is not perfectly reproducible due to the sudden and sometimes
34
35 random formation of a crack (Grosse and Ohtsu, 2010). This is especially true in AE observations
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37 of geologic materials.
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43 Just as in field microseismic monitoring, AE recordings of rock fracture tests in the
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45 laboratory can be difficult to interpret because AE only provides part of the story of rock response
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47 to loading. For instance, in brittle and heterogeneous materials it is difficult to determine the
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49 macro-scale fracture structure from individual AE events because throughout the loading and
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51 failure process, a damage zone is created where many AEs are generally observed and the scatter
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53 of locations can be moderate to quite large depending on scale of heterogeneities, boundary
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55 conditions, and mechanical properties. This microcrack damage zone eventually coalesces into a
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4 macro-scale fracture, but the observations throughout the test are often of the individual
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6 microcracks that could or could not be directly connected to the main coalesced fracture. This
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8 observation is the **motivation** for using cloud-based imaging techniques to determine overall
9
10 coalesced fracture location, orientation and roughness. The following will present and discuss a
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12 method to determine fracture structure in a cloud of events and the benefits and shortfalls of this
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14 approach.
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18 **TEST METHODS AND EQUIPMENT**

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21 An unconfined laboratory hydraulic fracture was carried out while monitoring AE with the
22
23 **motivation of quantifying overall** fracture structure from the discrete AEs observed relating to
24
25 microcracking. The following section describes the AE analysis, laboratory equipment, specimen
26
27 characteristics and testing procedures.
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31 **Acoustic emission analysis**

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33 Observed AE point source locations were used to develop a straightforward method for
34
35 macro-scale fracture identification. **The AE fracture identification process was then compared to**
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37 **the actual fracture surface observed from images post-test. AE fracture identification was**
38
39 **performed post-test and uses 3D AE event source location data to generate the predicted fracture**
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41 **plane. A method for identifying fracture surfaces based on unfiltered AE data was created. This**
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43 **method does not require previous knowledge of the fracturing directions or geometry. The**
44
45 **requirements for the** method are at a minimum a set of 3D AE event source location results.
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48 Additional data, such as AE event amplitudes, correlation coefficients, event time, and source
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50 mechanism solutions can be used for **data filtering to further enhance results by providing**
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52 **weighting factors if an event attribute is found to be more indicative of being associated with a**
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54 **macro-scale fracture plane than other parameters. Though additional information regarding the**
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4 individual AE microcrack observations can be used for filtering the observed dataset or
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6 determining weighting parameters, the process described here made no assumptions on the
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8 individual event contribution to macro-scale fracture, but instead used all located AE events.
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11 The method for creating the fracture plane from a cloud of data is an error reduction process
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13 in which a planar fracture is assumed and rotated in both the pitch and roll directions about a user
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15 specified origin and compared with AE event source location data. The comparison takes place by
16
17 calculating an error term from the perpendicular distances of each AE event source location found
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19 inside a set of bounds parallel to the rotated fracture plane, to the assumed plane. The bounds are
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21 user specified and can be optimized based on the cloud characteristics or determined a priori from
22
23 knowledge of the material and/or fracturing behavior expected. For the example discussed here,
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25 the bounds were specified from expected widths of the fracture process zone observed during
26
27 notched beam bending experiments (Hampton et al., 2012). **Fig. 1** and **2** show conceptual sketches
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29 of this rotated fracture plane and error estimation. **Fig. 1** shows an arbitrarily oriented plane
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31 residing within a grouping of AE events (red dots) with its center at a user specified origin. The
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33 principal axes of the plane are shown here to rotate so that the plane can be oriented in a discretized
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35 set of rotation angles. Computations are performed at each orientation iteration to determine the
36
37 quality of fit for that orientation amongst the AE source locations. **Fig. 2** shows a view parallel to
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39 the assumed fracture plane (purple), where the AE events may or may not reside within the
40
41 specified bounds (orange region). Axes y' and x' are the principal coordinate system axes for a
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43 given iteration in the pitch direction (i.e., figure shows the assumed fracture plane at an iteration
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45 angle of theta degrees in the roll direction with a given pitch orientation defined by x' and y').
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55 To perform the AE fracture identification process, a range of coordinates is selected for the
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57 center/origin of the assumed fracture plane. Typical origin locations were selected around the
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4 perimeter of the openhole fracturing interval as seen in the conceptual sketch in **Fig. 3**. The purpose
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6 of selecting multiple origin locations is to reduce the fracture surface error by alternating where
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8 the fracture can initiate. For instance, it is possible for fractures to initiate perpendicular or
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10 tangentially from the borehole wall because of near wellbore complexity and damage. This
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12 technique allows for gridding the entire specimen with possible origins if the actual fracture origin
13
14 is unknown. This would be useful in a very complex specimen with many pre-existing natural
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16 fractures that could be stimulated. Once a range of values has been selected for origin locations,
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18 pitch and roll axes are chosen. The assumed fracture plane is then aligned in an arbitrary orientation
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20 in the pitch and roll axis directions. An iteration frequency must be specified to determine how
21
22 coarse the fracture search will be in both the pitch and roll directions. For this work, iteration
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24 angles were spaced by no more than 2.5°.

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31 An error term is calculated for each iteration and can be represented in several ways, but
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33 for most testing it was determined that Equation (1) showed the highest accuracy results.

$$Error = \frac{\left(\frac{\sum \varepsilon_i}{n}\right)}{d} \quad 1$$

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43 where ε_i is the perpendicular distance from individual AE events to the assumed fracture plane
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45 within the chosen bounds, d is the total bounding distance assumed for the data, and n is the total
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47 number of AE events. The numerator in Equation (1) is the average perpendicular distance of all
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49 AE event source locations to the rotated fracture plane. The denominator is the total bounded
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51 distance between positive and negative bounds on either side of the rotated fracture plane. This
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53 term simplifies the overall error associated with the perpendicular distances from AE events to the
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55 assumed fracture plane in each iteration, but should show a relatively high accuracy if the
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4 assumption of a planar fracture is valid. A conceptual sketch of an error versus iteration angle plot
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6 is shown in **Fig. 4** for **three separate origin locations defined as the three colored lines**. This plot
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8 shows the possibility of differing origin locations having altered reductions in error. The main drop
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10 in error is evident in all three origin locations at nearly the same iteration angle and would suggest
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12 that if these origin locations are relatively close together, a macro-scale fracture exists in this
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14 location and orientation.
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18 **Test materials, equipment and procedure**

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21 The test material used was granite that was obtained from the Liesveld Quarry in Lyons,
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23 Colorado. Granite was chosen because of its high strength, relative homogeneity, and low
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25 permeability. Hydraulic fracture testing was performed using a dual pump fluid injection system.
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27 Data monitoring for the hydraulic fracturing tests included flow rate, pump pressure, wellhead
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29 pressure, and acoustic emissions.
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32 *Test materials*

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35 A granite sample with dimensions of 30x25x30 cm³ was used for the hydraulic fracturing
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37 test. The y-direction of the sample was slightly shorter than the others because the sample
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39 contained one unfinished and rough side, which made the sample a good candidate for unconfined
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41 testing because of the inability to put an irregularly shaped block into a loading apparatus. The
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43 granite material properties are found in **Table 1**. The elastic properties are reported from the
44
45 average of several unconfined compressive strength tests. Tensile strength was measured using the
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47 Brazilian tensile test. Fracture toughness was measured using a notched beam fracture toughness
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49 method. Using granite for this type of acoustic emission fracture prediction testing allowed for
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51 relatively large amounts of events to be recorded throughout the hydraulic fracture tests because
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53 of the brittle nature of the crystalline rock.
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4 *Equipment*
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7 Hydraulic injection was performed through a steel casing to a target openhole interval using
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9 a dual Teledyne ISCO syringe pump system. Injection well diameter and openhole fracturing
10 interval diameter were approximately 10 mm and 6 mm, respectively. The injection fluid was an
11 80-weight gear oil with an approximate viscosity of 120 cP. MISTRAS Group, Inc. acoustic
12 emission data collection hardware and software were used throughout all acoustic material
13 characterization and laboratory hydraulic fracture testing. A MISTRAS PCI-2-8 system was used,
14 which contained 3 PCI-2 boards and a total of 6 possible signal inputs. High sensitivity wideband
15 WS α piezoelectric transducers were used. Each sensor has operating frequency range of 100-1000
16 kHz and a resonance of 125 kHz. Custom AE data analysis software was built in MATLAB to
17 process the large number of AE signals in a relatively short period of time for source
18 characterization, moment tensor solutions, parametric hit data analysis and coalesced fracture
19 location and orientation prediction (Hampton et al., 2018). This work will focus on the latter;
20 coalesced fracture location and orientation prediction.
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38 *Test procedure*
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41 Prior to hydraulic fracture testing, sample characterization was performed using the AE
42 system to understand the material wave velocity, attenuation, and proper transducer location.
43 Active and passive AE testing was performed using Auto-Sensor Tests (ASTs) and pencil lead
44 break tests, respectively. ASTs operate each sensor in sequence as pulsers and receivers and with
45 known sensor locations, arrival times and signal initiation times, wave velocity structure could be
46 determined. Sample characterization was performed before and after drilling and casing the
47 wellbore to determine if significant changes within the velocity structure occurred providing
48 updates to the propagation velocity input in the MISTRAS source location software.
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4 Once all pre-test sample characterization was performed and the wellbore was drilled and
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6 cased the fracturing procedures could be initiated. Wellhead pressure was monitored using a T-
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8 junction and pressure transducer. Once trapped hydraulic system air was bled from the lines, a
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10 constant pressure injection interval was performed to check the casing for seal leaks. Upon
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12 completion of the constant pressure injection, the fracturing process was initiated at a constant
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14 flow rate of approximately 0.1 mL/min.
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18 19 **TEST RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS**

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21 The granite sample was hydraulically fractured under unconfined conditions through a steel
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23 casing to a target interval. The steel casing depth was approximately 100 mm, while the openhole
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25 interval length extended an additional 50 mm down into the specimen. The openhole interval was
26
27 originally intended to have a length of 100 mm starting from the cased depth to an overall bottom-
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29 hole depth of 200 mm, but a tough inclusion or layer existed within the granite sample, which
30
31 prevented drilling further. Hydraulic fracture orientation predictions could not be made prior to
32
33 stimulation because the sample was unstressed. Although the overall fracturing direction was not
34
35 estimated prior to testing, it was predicted that the hydraulic fracture would produce a larger and
36
37 more extensive network in the upper half of the sample because of the possible hard inclusion or
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39 layer encountered during the openhole interval drilling procedure.
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45 46 **AE source locations**

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48 Nearly 4,300 AE events were observed throughout the hydraulic fracturing experiment.
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50 **Fig. 5 (a)** shows the large cloud of observed AE events throughout the experiment. The amplitude
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52 of each event is represented proportionally to the sizes of the circles. The colors of each event
53
54 represent the correlation coefficient from the multiple regression analysis used in 3D source
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56 location. Red represents the highest correlation coefficient, meaning best location (1.0/1.0), and
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4 blue for the lowest correlation (0/1.0), with a color gradient between. From **Fig. 5** the apparent
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6 total depth of the majority of the fracture network generation appeared to stay above the bottom-
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8 hole of the well as predicted from encountering the stiff inclusion or layer during drilling.
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11 A secondary wellbore was required to be placed in the sample to test the ability to create a
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13 simulated injector-producer well scheme commonly found in geothermal reservoir exploitation.
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15 Secondary wellbore location optimization was difficult in such a large cloud of high amplitude
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17 and correlation coefficient AE events. It was desired that the second wellbore be located in a region
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19 of dense fracturing to provide a hydraulic connection between the original injection well and the
20
21 production well through the fracture network. In other words, a macro-scale hydraulic fracture
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23 location and orientation was desired. The AE events were filtered to only contain higher correlation
24
25 coefficient and amplitude data in efforts to pinpoint a main fracturing plane and/or a dense region
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27 of fractures believed to be hydraulically connected to the injection well. **Fig. 5 (b)** and **(c)** show
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29 these reductions and one main hydraulic fracture appeared to propagate in nearly the same
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31 orientation as the yz -plane. A very dense region of AE events existed approximately 40 mm away
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33 from the injection well at a depth of 100 mm. This region of events, coupled with the apparent
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35 direction of the main fracture was used as inputs in the secondary well trajectory plan. The second
36
37 wellbore was placed at an angle of 25° from the vertical in the positive x and z direction. This path
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39 was chosen to ensure if a hydraulic fracture existed in the yz -plane, the wellbore should pass
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41 through the fracture at some point as it traverses to the other side of the sample. **Fig. 6** shows the
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43 injection well and the angled production well in a reduced cloud of AE events. It was uncertain as
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45 to whether this wellbore location would be sufficient for a binary injector-producer scheme until
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47 flow through tests were performed.
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AE fracture surface predictions

A more advanced method of determining the location of fracture faces was desired for future tests because of the uncertainty associated with choosing a secondary wellbore location based only on amplitude and correlation coefficient filtered AE events. The method needed to be robust enough to just use AE location data and provide reasonable fracture orientation, extent, and direction from very dense clouds of data, where a coalesced fracture could not reliably be inferred. The method described above is a simple planar-based approach using distances from each AE event source location to an assumed fracture plane to determine optimal orientation of a predicted fracture.

The AE fracture detection process was applied to the data collected throughout the unconfined hydraulic fracturing test. The error determined from each of the iteration angles of the roll axis is shown in Fig. 7 from the lowest error pitch orientation. From this figure, the well-defined minimum error indicated that a fracture plane was likely in the orientation of approximately 1.7 radians from the positive roll axis. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the predicted hydraulic fracture appeared to intersect both the injection and production wells, which was later confirmed using fluid injection and recovery tests and post-test sample coring and slicing (Frash, 2012; Hampton, 2012).

The injection well was over-cored and removed to determine orientation of the actual fracture network. After over-coring, the granite block was slabbed at approximately one-inch intervals to view the existing hydraulic fracture network within the sample. Fig. 10 shows photos of the hydraulic fracture network stenciled for clearer view. The complex network within the block existed from several hydraulic fracture injection tests, some of the latter were not recorded with AE due to software buffering issues. The fracture data from the photographs were digitized and

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4 shown in **Fig. 11**. The dark blue points in this figure are digitized fracture locations from the
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6 photographs, while the light blue mesh represents the interpolated surface between the measured
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8 points. This complex fracture network in an unconfined sample shows how induced stress changes
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10 from the hydraulic fractures can alter re-fracture orientation and create quite a complex system of
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12 fractures. **Fig. 12** shows the hydraulic fracture from **Fig. 11** that is most nearly aligned with the
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14 predicted hydraulic fracture orientation determined. Comparisons made between the main
15
16 hydraulic fracture predicted from the AE data and the largest fracture observed in the network
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18 from the slabbed sample can be seen in **Fig. 13** and **Fig. 14**. Upon initial observations, the two
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20 fractures appeared to match in location, orientation and moderately in roughness trend. The
21
22 roughness of the predicted hydraulic fracture was determined based on the lateral variability
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24 observed at the lowest error plane orientation. Though roughness predictions from AE data are
25
26 interesting, the main take-away from these images are the general agreement between predicted
27
28 and actual hydraulic fracture orientation and extent.

35 DISCUSSIONS

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38 A procedure for using AE source locations to identify possible macro-scale fractures
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40 existing within the block was developed. The method is a simple planar-based approach where an
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42 error is calculated from the perpendicular distance of each AE event and an assumed fracture plane.
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44 The fracture plane is then rotated in both the pitch and roll directions to determine the lowest error
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46 orientation within the cloud of AE events. The method provided a very reliable estimation of a
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48 macro-scale hydraulic fracture as seen in the comparison images of the predicted fracture and the
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50 actual fracture, as measured from photographs taken from the slabbed block post-test.
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55 The AE predicted fracture was at an approximate 10° offset from the yz -plane. The
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57 complexity observed from the slabbed block photos show the hydraulic fracture network to be
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4 very complex and contain not only planar fractures, but also substantial fracture curvature. The
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6 assumed planar fracture matched very well in most regions until the actual fracture showed non-
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8 planar behavior, as seen closely in **Fig. 13** and **Fig. 14**.
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11 The applicability of this method is reliant on the ability to observe relatively large
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13 quantities of AE events associated with a few macro-scale coalesced fractures. This assumes that
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15 the observed AE cloud resulted in a coalesced fracture, and not just a highly damaged and isolated
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17 grouping of microcracks. For instance, two identical experimental setups would produce very
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19 different fracture structure if testing a densely naturally fractured material and a homogeneous and
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21 isotropic material. The same AE fracture prediction method applied to both tests would likely give
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23 rise to differing predicted fracture error.
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28 **SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS**

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30 An AE method to predict coalesced fracture structure, orientation and location is presented.
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32 Predictions of the coalesced fracture throughout laboratory hydraulic fracture testing in a brittle
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34 granite showed marked correlation with the actual fracture structure observed from coring and
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36 slabbing the specimen post-test. The following are the summary and conclusions from this work
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43 • A simple planar-based coalesced fracture structure prediction method was developed and
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45 validated against actual laboratory hydraulic fracture data and provided a reasonable
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47 correlation using only AE event source locations as input variables.
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51 • This method tends to break down when fracture structure alters from the assumed planar-
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53 based approach. Assuming non-planar fractures in regions of progressive low error might
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55 help mitigate this issue and provide a complex, but low error solution.
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- The ability to iterate through multiple origin locations for the macro-scale fracture structure prediction reduces the error associated with forcing a planar fracture to contain any specific coordinates. This functionality also allows the prediction of multiple fracture sets in a sample with a single run.

Further work is necessary to modify this process to include AE parametric data and/or source mechanism data as weighting factors for the refinement of a coalesced fracture prediction tool. Using AE event time would also serve to refine this method, as an iterative predictive tool that updates based on event time and location distribution; coalesced spline type geometry changes would also be a next step for incorporating complex curving fractures without the use of nonplanar fracture assumptions. The applicability of this method to other materials, specifically brittle civil engineering materials like concrete, is evident from this study. If AE observations are made within a concrete structure and post-observation measurement of the fractures is obstructed, this method could provide reasonable estimations of the extent and number of macro-scale fractures residing within the structure. Additional research is required to determine if this or a modified routine can more accurately define coalesced fractures occurring in less brittle materials or complex loading environments in which produce curved fractures.

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Table 1 Material properties of granite specimen used in the study (Frash, 2012; EMI, 2010; Morrell, 2012).

Material Property	Average
Young's modulus (GPa)	56.9
Poisson's ratio	0.32
UCS (MPa)	152
Density (g/cm ³)	2.63
Permeability (μD)	1.16
Porosity	0.0077
Tensile strength (MPa)	7.5
Fracture toughness (MPa·m ^{0.5})	0.72

Fig. 1 Conceptual sketch of AE events (red dots) and their proximity to a rotated fracture plane.

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Fig. 2 Error estimation from the perpendicular distance of each individual AE event to the fracture plane within a set of bounds. The x' and y' axes are the principal axes associated with the lowest error pitch orientation of the assumed plane. The plane is then rotated in increments of $\Delta\theta$ to perform an error estimation under each orientation. ϵ_i is the perpendicular distance between AE event (i) and the assumed fracture plane.

Fig. 3 Conceptual sketch of picking multiple origin locations around an openhole wellbore. The assumed origin locations can be user specified or gridded throughout the entire specimen if no a priori information exists.

Fig. 4 Conceptual sketch of an error versus iteration angle plot. The colors of the lines each represent a different origin location. The reductions in error can possibly signify the existence of a fracture plane with that iteration angle from the assumed origination orientation.

Fig. 5 AE event source locations showing very dense microcracking in the top half of the specimen. Correlation coefficient, or location accuracy, is shown by color where 1/1 represents no location error and 0/1 represents very large location error. The colorbar on the right shows the distribution of color gradient. AE event amplitude is represented by the relative sizes of the circles. (a) Raw AE events prior to filtering. (b) AE source locations filtered by only those containing higher than a 0.995/1.0 correlation coefficient and 40 dB amplitude. (c) AE source locations filtered by only those containing higher than a 0.995/1.0 correlation coefficient and 50 dB amplitude.

Fig. 6 3D view of the filtered AE event source locations and injection (vertical) and production (angled) wellbores.

Error Versus Iteration Angle

Fig. 7 Fracture surface fit error versus iteration angle showing one main hydraulic fracture and other possible secondary fracture orientations. The plot shows all 9 origin locations that were used (9 points surrounding a circular wellbore). The well-developed error minimum at approximately 1.7 radians in the roll direction for this particular lowest error pitch direction is shown.

Fig. 8 Predicted hydraulic fracture from AE data. AE source locations have been extensively filtered for viewing, but not for the fracture surface prediction procedure.

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Fig. 9 Predicted hydraulic fracture from AE data.

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Fig. 10 Slabbed sample photos showing complex network of hydraulic fractures stenciled for clearer view; depth increases from top left to bottom right.

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Fig. 11 All observed hydraulic fractures from slab photos. Dark blue circles represent the digitization of actual fracture locations from the images in Fig. 10. The light blue mesh is just an interpolated spline surface between these points.

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Fig. 12 Main hydraulic fracture visible from the slabbed sample data. Darker blue circles represent the individual data points digitized from the slab images. Lighter blue surface is an interpolation between the slab data.

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Fig. 13 Zoomed comparison between the AE predicted hydraulic fracture (black) and the digitized fracture location from the slab plots (blue).

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Fig. 14 Zoomed comparison between the AE predicted hydraulic fracture (black) and the digitized fracture location from the slab plots (blue).